

Influence of single walled carbon nanotubes on the effective elastic constants of poly(ethylen terephthalate)

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Abstract: Poly(ethylene terephthalate) (PET) is one of the most extensively used thermoplastic polyesters out on the market, and it has been implemented in many forms. There has been limited work in the area of PET reinforced with single walled carbon nanotubes (SWCNT) in mechanical properties. Nanocomposites based on PET with small contents of SWCNT were prepared by in situ polymerization. Elastic constants were determined by tensile tests performed on specimens instrumented with strain gauges. Assuming random orientation distribution of nanotubes, experimental Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio values were compared to some micromechanical models (Cox and Krenchel, Halpin-Tsai and Mori-Tanaka) which take into account orientation and aspect ratio of the nanotubes. However, the waviness of the nanotubes is a factor that influences the reinforcing efficiency.

Keywords:

A. Carbon nanotubes A. Nano composites B. Mechanical properties C. Elastic properties.

1. Introduction

Since discovered in 1990s, carbon nanotubes (CNT), including single-walled (SWCNT) and multi-walled (MWCNT), have attracted great interest in the academic and industrial community [1]. Theoretically, the tensile modulus and strength of a grapheme layer reach up to 1 TPa and 200 GPa, respectively [2, 3]. These values have been widely used to interpret the mechanical

properties of single-walled and multi-walled nanotubes. CNT have potential applications in many areas such as biosensors, conducting agents, field-effect transistors, nanocomposites, etc.

There are two key issues to be addressed in order to achieve superior performance in CNT filled polymer nanocomposites: dispersion of CNT in polymer matrix and interaction between CNT and polymer matrix. Recently, carbon nanotubes have been used as nano-reinforcement to enhance the mechanical strength of polymer matrices. An important increase of the tensile modulus and yield strength of polymers has been reported after random dispersion of single-walled and multi-walled CNT [4, 5]. In particular due to their large aspect ratio and mechanical properties, single walled (SWCNT) [6] are considered to be unique candidates for making polymer-based nanocomposites. Currently, melt mixing compounding, curing, in situ polymerization and coagulation are usually used to prepare these kinds of nanocomposites [7]. The main advantage of this method is that it enables a better nanotube dispersion and formation of a strong interface between the nanotube and the polymer matrix [8].

The prediction of the elastic properties of discontinuous-fiber-reinforced materials as a function of the volume fraction of the reinforcement has received much attention [9-13]. The most commonly used methods are: the rule of mixtures [11], the Cox shear-lag theory with an orientation factor to take into account the randomness of the discontinuous fibers in composites, [12, 13], the Halpin-Tsai equations [14] and the Mori-Tanaka model [15, 16].

A number of studies have been conducted on the mechanical properties of many CNT/polymers such as polystyrene (PS) [17] polycarbonate (PC) [18], polyethylene (PE) [19], poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) [20], poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA) [21], polyacrylonitrile (PAN) [22], polyimide (PI) [23] and epoxy resin [24]. Properties such as tensile and bending strengths and moduli, yield stress, fracture toughness, fatigue and friction were investigated. Poly(ethylene terephthalate) (PET) is one of the most widely used polymers in industrial applications. Some

studies have been focused on the morphology and mechanical properties, mainly Young's modulus and tensile strength, of the MWCN/PET composites [25]. Nevertheless, the number of research papers reporting the influence of SWCNT on the mechanical properties of PET is still limited, this lack of attention makes SWCNT/PET nanocomposites particularly interesting.

In this study, poly(ethylene terephthalate) (PET)/single walled carbon nanotube (SWCNT) composites were prepared by in situ polymerization. Tensile tests were performed to obtain their elastic constants: Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio. The effect of SWCNT content on the yield stress and the failure strain was also studied. The experimental results have been compared with some models proposed to evaluate the mechanical properties of composites as a function of the volume fraction of the reinforcement (Cox and Krenchel, Halpin-Tsai and Mori-Tanaka models) which considered the orientation distribution and aspect ratio of the nanotubes. Also, two models based on finite element method and Mori-Tanaka model, which take into account the curvature or waviness of the reinforcement, were compared to experimental results. Finally, the fracture surfaces of SWCNT/PET were studied and the failure mechanisms of this composite discussed.

2. Experimental techniques

2.1. Materials and sample fabrication

Nanocomposites based on PET and SWCNT (CNI Technology Co., TX, USA, synthesized by using the HiPco[®] method), several microns length and about 1.4 nm in diameter, as revealed by Raman spectroscopy, were prepared by in-situ polymerization. SWCNT were dispersed by ultrasonication and high-speed stirring in ethylene glycol (BASF, Germany). In situ polycondensation was then accomplished by transesterification with dimethyl terephthalate (Elana S.A., Torun, Poland) carried out in an acid-resistant steel reactor. The nanocomposite was

extruded from the reactor using compressed nitrogen. Different samples with SWCNT weight concentration between 0% and 0.3% were obtained. The pure PET presents a molecular weight of $M_w \approx 27600$ g/mol. The nanocomposite after extruded from the reactor was pelletized and injection molded into dog-bone bars with a total length of 60 mm, a rectangular cross section of 2×4 mm² and a gage length of 20 mm. The injection molding parameters were: injection pressure 70 MPa, melt temperature 260-270 °C, mould temperature 30 °C, hold time 6 s and cool time 20 s. Specimens of PET and SWCNT/PET nanocomposites with 0.1, 0.2 and 0.3 wt% of SWCNT content were prepared by the described procedure.

2.2. Density measurements

A Mettler Toledo balance, with a resolution of ± 0.001 mg, equipped with a density determination kit, was used to evaluate the change of density in PET by the incorporation of different contents of CNTs. Five measurements were done for each specimen and two specimens were measured for each kind of sample studied, determining the average values and their standard deviation.

2.3. Mechanical testing

In order to obtain elastic and strength properties of these composites, uniaxial tensile tests were performed using dog-bone shaped specimens on an electromechanical testing machine (MTS Alliance RT/5). Although the strain was measured during the tests with an extensometer attached to the sample (model MTS DX2000); the specimens tested were also instrumented with strain gauges to measure simultaneously longitudinal and transversal strain. Each strain gauge was connected in a $\frac{1}{4}$ Wheatstone bridge configuration and the signal transmitted was recorded by a signal conditioner which allows assure a correct calibration of the whole device.

2.4. Fractography

After performing the tensile tests of the samples of PET polymer and the three composites with different content of SWCNT, the fracture surfaces have been characterized by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The samples were vacuum coated with a thin gold film by the sputtering technique before being analyzed using a Hitachi S3400N scanning electron microscope.

3. Results

3.1. Density measurements

The nanocomposites' density was measured by the water immersion method. The theoretical value was calculated, assuming there are no voids, by the rule of mixtures:

$$\rho_c = \frac{1}{\left(\frac{M_{cnt}}{\rho_{cnt}}\right) + \left(\frac{M_m}{\rho_m}\right)} \quad (1)$$

where ρ_i is the density and M_i denotes the mass fraction of the composite (c), single-walled nanotubes (cnt) and the matrix (m). The density of carbon nanotubes was 1.71 g/cm³ [26]. For this calculus, it was supposed that the density of the nanoreinforcement is not modified during the fabrication process.

Taking into account the classical theory of composites with micro-scale reinforcements, the density values allow determining the volume fraction of voids (V_v) in a composite [27]:

$$V_v = 1 - \rho_{c \text{ exp}} \left(\frac{M_{cnt}}{\rho_{cnt}} + \frac{M_m}{\rho_m} \right) \quad (2)$$

The volume fraction of voids of nanocomposites, calculated from the experimental density values ($\rho_{c\ exp}$) provide negative results, indicating that this estimation is not right for composites materials reinforced with nano-reinforcements.

For all the nanoreinforcement contents considered, the experimental density is higher than the theoretical one (Fig. 1). This means that the added SWCNT do not occupy an additional volume and it could indicate that the nanofiller partially occupies the free volume of the PET network, concluding that a densification of the polymer, determined by an increase of its bulk density, is mainly associated to a loss in the free volume.

This increment of density could also be associated with the lack of defects, a signal of good dispersion of nanoreinforcements when the content of SWCNT is beneath these low values.

The volume fraction of SWCNT (V_{cnt}) was calculated from the mass fraction (M_{cnt}), assuming two phases and no-trapped air:

$$V_{cnt} = \frac{M_{cnt}}{M_{cnt} + (1 - M_{cnt}) \frac{\rho_{cnt}}{\rho_m}} \quad (3)$$

3.2. Mechanical properties measurement

Fig. 2 shows the typical experimental stress-strain curves of the SWCNT/PET composites. The Young's modulus, E , yield stress, σ_y , and maximum failure strain, ε_f were obtained using the average of five values obtained from the stress-strain curves for each case. Poisson's ratio, ν , was determined from the longitudinal and transversal strain signals. The experimental results are listed in Table 1.

The yield stress and the Young's modulus increased 6.5% and 11.9% respectively, when 0.3% CNTs was added. The failure strain, on the other hand, decreases 89.1%. Also the Poisson's ratio decreases 3.2% for the highest SWCNT content added.

3.3. Morphology of fracture surfaces

Fig. 3 collects the SEM fractographs from the fractured specimens. The shown micrographs are representative of the entire surface. Unreinforced matrix (Figures 3a and 3b) shows a rougher fracture surface, characteristic of a ductile material. Nevertheless, the addition of SWCNT provides a much smooth fracture surface with some signs of brittle fracture (Figures 3c and 3d). This observation is in agreement with the values of yield stress and failure strain presented in Table 1.

4. Discussion

4.1. Modelling of elastic constants

The elastic modulus of a polymer reinforced with CNTs is generally determined by the elastic properties of its components (CNTs and matrix), aspect ratio and volume fraction of the reinforcement. Since the modulus of CNTs is usually much higher than that of the polymer matrices, a higher composite modulus is expected by adding CNTs to matrix. Several empirical or semi-empirical equations have been proposed to predict the modulus of CNTs-polymer composites and some of them have been applied to the data obtained in this work.

The simplest way to model the effective properties of a two-phase material containing fibers and matrix is the rule of mixtures. This model assumes iso-stress or iso-strain criteria depending on the way in which the fibers are arranged (series or parallel) and can be used as an upper and a lower bound of the composite modulus.

$$E^{*(upper)} = E_{cnt} V_{cnt} + E_m (1 - V_{cnt}) \quad (4)$$

$$E^{*(lower)} = \left[V_{cnt} E_{cnt}^{-1} + (1 - V_{cnt}) E_m^{-1} \right]^{-1} \quad (5)$$

But this model considers continuous and parallel orientated reinforcement in the composite. In the theory of short-fiber reinforced composites, the rule of mixtures was modified by Cox [14]

and Krenchel [15]. These models estimate the composite modulus taken into account the effects of fiber length and orientation. The predictions obey the following expression:

$$E_c = E_m(1 - V_{cnt}) + \eta_L \eta_O E_{cnt} V_{cnt} \quad (6)$$

where η_L is a factor of the reinforcement length (l), η_O is the orientation factor, V_{cnt} the volumetric fraction of reinforcement and, E_m and E_{cnt} are the modulus of elasticity of matrix and nanotubes, respectively. The reinforcement length factor η_L was calculated according to:

$$\eta_L = \left(1 - \frac{\tanh\left(\frac{\beta l}{2}\right)}{\frac{\beta l}{2}} \right) \text{ with } \beta = \frac{1}{r} \left[\frac{E_m}{E_{cnt} (1 + \nu_m) \ln\left(\frac{R}{r}\right)} \right] = \frac{1}{r} \left[\frac{E_m}{E_{cnt} (1 + \nu_m) \ln\left(\frac{\pi}{4V_{cnt}}\right)} \right] \quad (7)$$

where ν_m is the matrix Poisson's ratio, r the fiber radius, and $2R$ the mean inter-nanotubes spacing, which in a square fiber packing system is $2r\sqrt{\pi / 4V_{cnt}}$.

The orientation factor η_O was calculated according to:

$$\eta_O = \frac{\sum_i a_{cnt_i} \cos^4 \varphi_i}{\sum_i a_{cnt_i}} \quad (8)$$

where a_{cnt_i} is the ratio between the cross sectional area presented by a group of nanotubes orientated at an angle φ_i to the applied load and the total area of all the fibers at a given cross section of the composite.

The Halpin-Tsai equation [14] represents a semi-empirical model based on data and geometry. It was originally used for composites with unidirectional reinforcement,

$$E_c = \frac{1 + c\eta V_{cnt}}{1 - \eta V_{cnt}} E_m \quad \eta = \frac{(E_{cnt} / E_m) - 1}{(E_{cnt} / E_m) + c} \quad (9)$$

in which $c=2(l/d)$ is a constant shape factor related to the aspect ratio of reinforcement length l and diameter d . In our nanocomposite, with SWCNT of approximated 1.4 nm of diameter and few microns before fabrication, c was chosen as 1000.

The Halpin-Tsai model was later modified using a parameter α , called orientation factor in this study, to account for the randomness of the discontinuous fibers [28]. If the fiber length is greater than the thickness of specimen, the fibers are assumed randomly oriented in two dimensions; and the parameter $\alpha= 1/3$ is used for the Young's modulus of the material. If the fiber length is much smaller than the thickness of the specimen, the fibers are assumed randomly oriented in three dimensions; and the parameter $\alpha = 1/6$ is used. In this study, the effective lengths of SWCNTs are about few microns long, which is much shorter than the thickness of specimens; therefore, three dimensional SWCNTs distribution is assumed for SWCNTs/PET composites. The orientation factor $\alpha= 1/6$ is chosen to modify the Halpin–Tsai equation as below:

$$E_c = \frac{1 + c\eta V_{cnt}}{1 - \eta V_{cnt}} E_m \quad \eta = \frac{(\alpha E_{cnt} / E_m) - 1}{(\alpha E_{cnt} / E_m) + c} \quad (10)$$

The model of Mori-Tanaka estimates the effective moduli of composites taking into account the average strain of an Eshelby ellipsoidal inclusion embedded in a solid containing many dispersed inclusions. Evidently, it is difficult to determine the exact solution due to the large number of interacting particles whose orientations and locations are often distributed statistically. Therefore, some simplifications or approximations are necessary. On one hand, the medium surrounding an inclusion is disturbed by the complex microstructure, and then its stiffness is different from the original matrix. Conversely, the stress field around an inclusion is perturbed due to the existence of other particles.

The effective stiffness tensor \mathbf{C}_c of the composite computed using the Mori-Tanaka's method [15] adapted by Benveniste [16],

$$\mathbf{C}_c = \mathbf{C}_m + V_{cnt} \{(\mathbf{C}_{cnt} - \mathbf{C}_m) \mathbf{A}\} \quad (11)$$

where \mathbf{C}_m , is the matrix phase stiffness tensor and \mathbf{C}_{cnt} the nanotubes one. For Mori–Tanaka’s method the concentration tensor \mathbf{A} can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{A}^{(dil)} \left[V_m \mathbf{I} + V_{cnt} \{ \mathbf{A}^{(dil)} \} \right]^{-1} \quad (12)$$

where $V_m=1-V_{cnt}$ is the matrix volume ratio and \mathbf{I} is the fourth order unit tensor. For Mori-Tanaka’s method, $\mathbf{A}^{(dil)}$ is the concentration tensor and for a dilute solution can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{A}^{(dil)} = \left[\mathbf{I} + \mathbf{S} \mathbf{C}_m^{-1} (\mathbf{C}_{cnt} - \mathbf{C}_m) \right]^{-1} \quad (13)$$

where \mathbf{S} the fourth order Eshelby’s tensor. The expression of Eshelby’s tensor can be found in elsewhere [29]. Braces denote average all possible orientations, this is

$$\{ \mathbf{A}^{(dil)} \} = \frac{1}{8\pi^2} \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^\pi \mathbf{A}^{(dil)} f(\theta, \phi, \psi) \sin \theta d\theta d\phi d\psi \quad (14)$$

where $f(\theta, \phi, \psi)$ is the orientation distribution function described using Euler’s angles. Since the nanotubes are assumed to be randomly oriented in the PET matrix, the distribution function is uniform and given by

$$f(\theta, \phi, \psi) = 1 \quad (15)$$

4.2. Discussion

The results obtained from the tensile tests show that the addition of SWCNT in PET makes the nanocomposite stiffer (higher elastic modulus), harder (higher yield stress) and more brittle (lower failure strain. The rapid decrease of failure strain with SWCNT content, which is normal to composites, is believed to be caused by premature failure starting at the SWCNT aggregates.

Fig. 4 shows the experimental results obtained in the tensile tests for Young’s modulus. Experimental values are compared with theoretical predictions using the Cox and Krenchel equation, the Halpin-Tsai model and Mori-Tanaka method.

To implement the micromechanical models the appropriate modulus and volume fraction should be assigned to the SWCNT. In the literature, experimental results for SWCNT modulus vary from 0.81TPa [29] to 1.25 TPa [30]. In this study, Young's modulus of 1 TPa and Poisson's ratio of 0.265 have been assumed according to the works of Goze et al. [31] and Ye et al. [32] based on the nanotube diameter. The Young's modulus and the Poisson's ratio of the PET matrix used were those determined from the tensile tests.

Independently on the model used, theoretical values of elastic modulus of PET composites are higher than the experimental results. The micromechanical models consider the orientation and aspect ratio, but the nanotube curvature is not taken into account. Because of the nanotubes may be curved, its high Young's modulus will not be fully exploited in the composite. Fisher et al. [33] developed a hybrid method of finite element modelling and classical micromechanics techniques (Mori-Tanaka method). The response of the nanotubes depends on the ratio of the nanotube and polymer moduli and the relationship between the diameter and the sinusoidal shape of the wavy nanotube. The authors characterized in a previous work the structure and morphology of the composites [7]. They observed good dispersion of nanotubes with the in-situ polymerization preparation technique as the nanotubes ropes could be observed isolated and homogeneously distributed. Nevertheless, the nanotubes did not appear straight and were clearly waved. Two nanotube waviness distributions (minimal waviness and more moderate waviness) obtained from the bibliography [33] have been used to calculate their effect in the effective modulus of the SWCNT/PET composites (Table 2). Decrease about 3.5% was obtained compared to the straight nanotubes assumption and good correlation between experimental data and the moderate waviness distribution can be observed. This means that a moderate waviness in the nanotubes can be justified the difference observed between the experimental data and the micromechanical predictions. Shao et al. [34] also proposed a model to predict the effect of

curvature on the effective elastic constants of the nanocomposites based on the finite element calculations made by Fisher. The reinforcing effect of a curved nanotube was simulated projecting the waved nanotube onto the vertical and horizontal directions as three fibers of different length. Fig. 4 shows the effective Young's modulus predicted by Shao is very closed to that obtained by using the Fisher model. Although a small increase in Young's modulus values is obtained. The reason for these differences may be a consequence of replacing a wavy nanotube by only one straight fiber in the chord direction (Fisher model) by three fibers (Shao model), one in the chord direction and two in the perpendicular direction. According to the previous discussion (Fig. 4) simple micromechanical models used in the first part of this work cannot be applied directly to the SWCNT-composites, without taking into account the curving and coiling effects. With respect to Poisson's ratio, a comparison of experiments and micromechanical predictions is shown in Fig. 5. The modified rule of mixtures cannot explain the decrease observed with the nanotubes content. The values predicted by the Mori-Tanaka model are also a bit higher than the experimental data, although it captures much better the effect of SWCNT as reinforcement in the transversal deformation. Nevertheless, it is evident that the SWCNT inhibit the lateral contraction more than what is expected by micromechanical models.

Finally, some influence was also detected in the plastic properties. Yield stress exhibit minor increase with SWCNT content, but the failure strain is dramatically reduced. The experimental results are presented in Table 1, and as it was remarked previously, these results agree with the observations by SEM of the surfaces of PET and SWCNT/PET nanocomposites.

Conclusions

In summary, nanocomposites of PET reinforced with small quantities of carbon nanotubes were prepared by in situ polymerization. Some important properties of SWCNT-reinforced PET composites have been studied. The results showed that the Young's modulus increase

continuously with the volume fraction of SWCNT added, while the Poisson ratio's decreases.

About the plastic properties of the PET and its nanocomposites, yield stress exhibits minor increase with SWCNT content, but the failure strain is dramatically reduced with the presence of SWCNT.

These data were compared to some micromechanical models: Cox and Krenchel, Halpin-Tsai and Mori-Tanaka. These models consider the random orientation of the nanotubes and their slenderness (aspect ratio diameter/length). But the comparison showed the micromechanical models overestimate the effect of the reinforcement. One issue which has not typically been associated with the modelling is the characteristic waviness or curvature of embedded nanotubes which can drastically reduce the effective stiffness of the nanotubes compared to straight nanotube models. There is little study on this item and to address this question two models based on finite element simulation and micromechanics were also compared to experimental results using a hypothetical moderate waviness distribution. Good agreement with these models was obtained, while at the moment it is impossible to isolate the effects of nanotube waviness from other reinforcement-limiting mechanisms. These results demonstrate that the micromechanical models (Cox and Krenchel, Halpin-Tsai and Mori-Tanaka models) cannot be applied directly to SWCNT composites and new models including the waviness effect on reinforcement capacity should be used.

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Figure captions

Fig. 1. Experimental and calculated value of density of PET nanoreinforced with different content of CNTs.

Fig. 2. Typical stress-strain curves for the unreinforced PET (a) and the SWCNT/PET composites with different content of SWCNT (b)

Fig. 3. SEM micrographs showing fracture surfaces of neat PET (a and b) and composite with 0.3wt% SWCNT (c and d).

Fig. 4. Predicted and experimental Young's modulus results as a function of SWCNT volume fraction. (a) Comparison to the micromechanical models of Cox and Krenchel, Halpin-Tsai and Mori-Tanaka is shown. (b) Comparison to the models of Fisher and Shao which take into account the waviness of the reinforcement on the effective Young's modulus is presented.

Fig. 5. Predicted (Mori-Tanaka method and rule of mixtures) and experimental Young's modulus results as a function of SWCNT volume fraction.

Tables

Table1. Experimental values of mechanical properties from tensile tests.

Nanotubes weight fraction (wt%)	Nanotubes volume fraction (%V _{cnt})	Young's Modulus E (GPa)	Poisson's ratio ν	Yield stress σ_y (MPa)	Maximum Failure strain ϵ_f (%)
0	0	2.60±0.01	0.438±0.008	58.2±0.2	460
0.1	0.078	2.68±0.05		58.5±1.2	103
0.2	0.157	2.78±0.05	0.432±0.005	60.0±1.8	70
0.3	0.235	2.91±0.08	0.424±0.003	62.0±0.7	50

Table 2. Effective reinforcing modulus, two nanotube waviness distributions from the bibliography [44] and a hypothetical one proposed to model the SWCNT/PET studied.

Waviness	$E_{\text{effective}}$	SWCNT phase volume	
$w=a/\lambda$	(GPa)	fraction	
	[58]	Distribution 1	Distribution 2
	0	1000	0.4
0.05	800	0.4	0.15
0.1	500	0.2	0.3
0.25	90	0	0.3
0.5	18	0	0.2

Figures

Fig. 1.

Fig. 2.

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

Fig. 5